

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-3-222-IG-2% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	49	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 3 222
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/8/2023 4:37:52 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 5:31:10 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.189	1617146	50.15	128530
2	7.773	1607717	49.85	121727

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-3-211-IG-2% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	49	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 3 211
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/8/2023 4:57:30 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 5:32:27 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.177	864171	99.04	64453
2	7.751	8406	0.96	827